

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF KETO-ACIDS. ACTION OF SODIUM ETHOXIDE ON DIETHYL CYCLOPENTANONE-2-CARBOXYLATE-2-ACETATE.

BY NRIPENDRA NATH CHATTERJEE, BASANTA KUMAR DAS
AND GIRINDRA NATH BARPUJARI.

Diethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate* yields ethyl 5-carbethoxy*cyclopentanone-2-acetate* by the action of sodium ethoxide in alcoholic solution.

During an investigation on the synthesis of carvestrene it was observed by Perkin and co-workers (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1909, 95, 2010) that ethyl pentane- $\alpha\delta\epsilon$ -tricarboxylate (I) is cyclised in presence of sodium in benzene to ethyl *cyclohexanone-3:6*-dicarboxylate (II), although there is the possibility of the formation of the other isomer namely, ethyl 5-carbethoxy-*cyclopentanone-2-acetate* (III, R=H).

In course of a synthetic work it is observed that diethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate*, obtained from ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate* and ethyl chloroacetate, is transformed by boiling sodium ethoxide into 5-carbethoxy*cyclopentanone-2-acetate* (III, R=H), the mechanism being obviously alcoholysis to ester (I) and subsequent ring-closure in a new position. It is our experience, however, that the five carbon ring is almost invariably formed in preference to the six carbon ring, where the two possibilities simultaneously exist. The constitution of the ester (III) is established by hydrolysis to *cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid* (IV, R=H). As it is quite possible that *cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid* may be obtained from the unchanged ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate*, an additional rigid proof of the constitution of the ester is afforded herein. Diethyl 5-carbethoxy*cyclopentanone-2-acetate-5-propionate* (VI), obtained by the action of ethyl β -chloropropionate on the sodium salt of (III, R=H), on hydrolysis yields an acid which is identical in all respects with *cyclopentanone-2-acetic-5-propionic acid* (VIII), prepared by a rational synthesis.

Ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-propionate*, obtained by the action of ethyl β -chloropropionate on the sodium salt of ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate*, is transformed by boiling sodium ethoxide into ethyl 5-carbethoxy*cyclopentanone-2-propionate* (V, R=H). The possibility of the formation of a six carbon ring does not exist in this case. Diethyl 5-carbethoxy*cyclopentanone-2-propionate-5-acetate* (VII), obtained by the action

of ethyl chloroacetate on (V, R=H) yields the required *cyclopentanone-2-acetic-5-propionic acid* (VIII, R=CH₂) on hydrolysis.

That the transformation product is not a mixture of the esters (II) and (III, R=H) is evident from the observation that ethyl *cyclopentanone-2-acetate*, obtained as a product of hydrolysis and esterification of the transformation product, yields an almost quantitative yield of a semicarbazone having melting point and mixed melting point 174° (*cf.* Linstead and Meade, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 935).

Diethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2:5-diacetate (III, R=CH₂·CO₂·Et) and diethyl 5-carbethoxy-*cyclopentanone-2:5-dipropionate* (V, R=CH₂·CH₂·CO₂Et), obtained by introducing an acetic acid and propionic acid residue in esters (III, R=H) and (V, R=H) respectively, yield *cyclopentanone-2:5-diacetic acid* and *cyclopentanone-2:5-dipropionic acid* on hydrolysis.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Ethyl 5-Carboxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (III, R=H).—Diethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate, required for the preparation of the above compound, was prepared as follows :—Finely divided metallic sodium (7.4 g.) in dry benzene (267 c.c.) was slowly treated with ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (50 g.). The mixture was then refluxed on the water-bath for 2 hours. It was allowed to cool and ethyl chloroacetate (44 g.) added and further refluxed for 4 hours. It was then cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether-benzene layer was washed with water, dried over calcium chloride, the solvents removed and the residual oil was distilled at $142-44^{\circ}/4$ mm. A mixture of diethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate (80 g.) and alcoholic sodium ethoxide (8.3 g. sodium and 138 c.c. of alcohol) was refluxed for 8 hours on the sand-bath. The product was treated with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether, the ethereal extract was washed with water, dried over sodium sulphate and the ether removed. It was then distilled at $160-65^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 60 g. It gives deep violet colouration with ferric chloride (*cf.* Perkin and co-workers, *loc. cit.*). (Found : C, 59.87; H, 7.5. $C_{12}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 59.5; H, 7.4 per cent).

cyclopentanone-2-acetic Acid (IV, R=H).—The above ester was hydrolysed with two volumes of boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid. Hydrolysis was completed in 1 hour and 5 hours more were required for decarboxylation. After removal of the mineral acid under reduced pressure, cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid was distilled at $170-80^{\circ}/5$ mm. as an oil which soon solidified, m.p. $51-53^{\circ}$ (mixed m.p.) (Linstead and Meade, *loc. cit.*).

The *semicarbazone* of the above keto-acid crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 198° . (Found : N, 21.0. $C_8H_{13}O_3N_3$ requires N, 21.1 per cent). *cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid* was also obtained by the method of Linstead and Meade (*loc. cit.*) in order to compare the m.p. of its semicarbazone with that of the above keto-acid. In a typical experiment 5 g. of ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2-acetate was hydrolysed with two volumes of boiling concentrated hydrochloric acid. After removal of the mineral acid under reduced pressure, cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid was distilled at $170-80^{\circ}/5$ mm., as an oil which soon solidified. It was converted into semicarbazone in the usual manner. The semicarbazone melted at 198° in agreement with that of the above keto-acid (mixed m.p.).

Semicarbazone of Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-acetate.—*cyclopentanone-2-acetic acid*, obtained as described above, was esterified by keeping overnight at room temperature with 3 parts of alcohol saturated with hydrogen chloride.

It was obtained in 90% yield, b.p. $123^{\circ}/13$ mm. The semicarbazone, obtained in an almost quantitative yield, melted at 174° (cf. Linstead and Meade, *loc. cit.*).

Diethyl 5-Carbethoxycyclopentanone-2 : 5-diacetate (III, R = CO₂Et).—Ethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (60 g.) was heated with a suspension of molecular sodium (6.5 g.) in benzene (120 c.c.) for 2 hours. The orange liquid was cooled and ethyl chloroacetate (40 c.c.) introduced and the mixture refluxed for 5 hours. The reaction product was mixed with water and a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the ester was isolated by means of ether, ether washed, dried and the ether removed. It was then distilled at $190-200^{\circ}/8$ mm., yield 30 g. (Found : C, 58.3; H, 7.2. C₁₆H₂₄O₇ requires C, 58.5; H, 7.3 per cent).

cyclopentanone-2 : 5-diacetic Acid.—A mixture of the above ester (30 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (240 c.c.) was refluxed for 1 hour and the clear solution evaporated to dryness, finally under reduced pressure. The residual crystalline solid was washed with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate and then with a little water, dried at 100° , and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum, m.p. 177° , yield 18 g. (Found : C, 53.9; H, 5.94. C₉H₁₂O₅ requires C, 54.0; H, 6.0 per cent).

The *diethyl ester* was prepared by esterification of the above acid (10 g.) by means of alcohol (50 c.c.) saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0° . It was kept overnight and then refluxed for 7 hours. After dilution it was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium carbonate solution, then with water. After removal of ether, it was distilled at $168-170^{\circ}/6$ mm, yield 8 g. (Found : C, 60.8; H, 7.75. C₁₃H₂₀O₅ requires C, 60.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate-5-propionate (VI).—Ethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-acetate (15 g.) was heated with a suspension of molecular sodium (1.6 g.) in benzene (30 c.c.) for 2 hours. The orange liquid was cooled and ethyl β -chloropropionate (10 c.c.) introduced and the mixture was refluxed for 5 hours. The reaction product was mixed with water and a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the ester was isolated by means of ether, ether washed, dried and the ether removed. It was then distilled at $200^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 10 g. (Found : C, 59.7; H, 7.4. C₁₇H₂₆O₇ requires C, 59.65; H, 7.6 per cent).

cyclopentanone-2-acetic-5-propionic Acid (VIII).—A mixture of the above ester (10 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (80 c.c.) was refluxed for 1 hour and the clear solution was then evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue crystallised and the solid was collected, washed with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate and then with a little

water, dried at 100° , and recrystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum, m.p. 126° , yield 5 g. (Found : C, 56.6; H, 6.4. $C_{10}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 56.1; H, 6.5 per cent).

The *diethyl ester* was prepared by esterifying the above acid (5 g.) by means of alcohol (25 c.c.), saturated with hydrogen chloride at 0° . It was kept overnight and then refluxed for 7 hours. After dilution it was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium carbonate solution, and then with water. After removal of ether, it was distilled at $170^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 62.2; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{22}O_4$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Carboxycyclopentanone-2-propionate (V, R=H).—Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate was prepared in the following manner Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate (52 g.) was added to molecular sodium (8 g.) in benzene (400 c.c.). After 1 hour the sodium compound was cooled and slowly treated with ethyl β -chloropropionate (41 g.). After heating for 5 hours more on the steam-bath, the mixture was acidified and the benzene layer was washed with sodium carbonate solution. Ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate (56 g., b. p. $189^{\circ}/18$ mm.) was obtained. A mixture of ethyl cyclopentanone-2-carboxylate-2- β -propionate (45 g.) and alcoholic sodium ethoxide (4.5 g. of sodium in 66 c.c. of alcohol) was refluxed for 8 hours on the sand-bath. The product was treated with ice-cold dilute sulphuric acid and extracted with ether and after removing ether it was distilled at $175^{\circ}/4$ mm. It gives deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride, yield 26 g. (Found : C, 60.9; H, 7.8. $C_{13}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 60.9; H, 8.1 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Carboxycyclopentanone-2-propionate-5-acetate (VII).—Ethyl 5-carboxycyclopentanone-2-propionate (26 g.) was heated with a suspension of sodium powder (2.8 g.) in benzene (55 c.c.) for 2 hours. The orange liquid was cooled and ethyl chloroacetate (13 g.) introduced and the mixture refluxed for 5 hours. The reaction product was mixed with water and a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the ester was isolated by means of ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. It was then distilled at $205^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 15 g. (Found : C, 59.8; H, 7.4. $C_{17}H_{26}O_7$ requires C, 59.65; H, 7.6 per cent).

cyclopentanone-2-acetic-5-propionic Acid (VIII).—A mixture of ethyl 5-carboxycyclopentanone-2-propionate-5-acetate (15 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (120 c.c.) was refluxed for 1 hour and the clear solution was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The residue crystallised and the solid was collected, washed with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate

and then with little water, dried at 100° , and recrystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum, m.p. 126° (mixed m.p.), yield 6 g. (Found : C, 56.1; H, 6.6. $C_{10}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 56.1; H, 6.5 per cent).

Ethyl 5-Carbethoxycyclopentanone-2 : 5-dipropionate (V, $R = CH_2 \cdot CH_2 \cdot CO_2Et$).—Ethyl 5-carbethoxycyclopentanone-2-propionate (48 g.) was heated with a suspension of sodium powder (5.2 g.) in benzene (100 c.c.) for 2 hours. The cold liquid was treated with ethyl β -chloropropionate (24 g.) and the mixture refluxed for 5 hours. The reaction product was mixed with water and a few drops of hydrochloric acid and the ester was isolated with ether. The ethereal extract was washed with water, dried and the solvent removed. It was then distilled at $215^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 60.9; H, 8.1. $C_{18}H_{28}O_7$ requires C, 60.7; H, 7.8 per cent).

cyclopentanone-2 : 5-dipropionic Acid.—A mixture of ethyl 5-carbethoxy-cyclopentanone 2 : 5-dipropionate (25 g.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) was refluxed for 1 hour and the clear solution was then evaporated under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was collected, washed with saturated aqueous ammonium sulphate and then with a little water, dried at 100° and crystallised from a mixture of ethyl acetate and petroleum ether, m.p. 122° . (Found : C, 57.9; H, 6.8. $C_{11}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 57.9; H, 6.8 per cent).

The *diethyl ester* was prepared by esterification of the above acid by means of alcohol saturated at 0° with hydrogen chloride. It was kept overnight and then refluxed for 7 hours. After dilution it was extracted with ether, the ethereal extract washed with sodium carbonate, water and dried. After removing ether, the ester was distilled at $172^{\circ}/4$ mm. (Found : C, 63.6; H, 8.4. $C_{15}H_{24}O_5$ requires C, 63.3; H, 8.4 per cent).

Our respectful thanks are due to Sir P. C. Ray and Dr. P. C. Mitter for their kind interest in the work.

SIR P. C. RAY FELLOW'S LABORATORY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE AND
TECHNOLOGY, CALCUTTA.

Received November 15, 1939.